

DEBT'S CONTRIBUTION TO RETURN ON EQUITY, A CONCEPTUAL AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS.

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Abstract

Financial management is the most important functional area of a business organization, the prime objective of any business is to maximize its profit, there are many factors which impact profit and a better capital structure can raise profits by lowering the firm's cost of capital. There are various possibilities or formats which ultimately exhibit the appropriate capital structure given in the situation prevailing. This paper attempts to describe different capital structure models and present scenarios which exhibit appropriate situations for employing debt in the capital structure of companies using empirical evidence and shows how the debt positively impacts the earnings of equity shareholders. This paper also dwells that a company's cost of equity may not be a reason for concern and portrays cost of equity as just a benchmark to minimize the shareholders expectation from the company. This paper benefits the companies in understanding the role of debt in the capital structure and alters the understanding about the cost of equity.

1.0 Introduction:

A Company needs financial resources to operate and expand, debt and equity capital are the main sources of capital structure of a company hence, the companies raise financial capital through the sale of equity shares and the issuance of debt securities and determines the ideal balance between debt and equity capital technically called as debt-equity ratio. The ratio of debt-equity in a company's capital structure affects various aspects of risk and return. The target capital structure of a company may therefore be determined by the company's management using a careful and thorough procedure[1]. The management is usually confronted with a quandary when deciding a capital structure of their company, because each company perceives debt-equity ratio differently[2]. There are possibilities to go with more equity and less debt component or otherwise and come up with an optimum capital structure given the situation. There are theories that have been evolved to address the conundrum of determining the capital structure including, Net Income Approach, Net Operating income Approach and Modigliani and Miller Approach. Thereafter, the topic of capital structure itself has been one of the most divisive topics in financial theory. The founding works of Modigliani and Miller were the seeds of this discussion [4,5,6], following which several studies have been published that have attempted to explicate the optimal capital structure through multiple dimensions [6,7,8,9,10,11,12].

Correspondingly, numerous studies that describe how debt capital can be employed in the capital structure to decrease the total capital costs; there is not much research that explains the proper situation for employing debt capital [13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21]. The paper seeks to compare and analyze the situations and describe different capital structure model and present scenarios which exhibit the appropriate situation for a mix of debt in the capital structure of a company. This paper also dwells that a company's cost of equity may not be a reason for concern and portrays cost of equity as just a benchmark to minimize the shareholders expectation from the company. This paper benefits companies to comprehend how debt increases shareholder returns and alter their impression about the cost of equity. The remaining paper has been structured as follows,

Section 2, the paper provides critical analyses of some of the more popular capital structure theories, including the Modigliani Miller Approach, Net Income Approach, and Net Operating Income Approach. Section 3, presents two scenarios that illustrate how the usage of debt capital boosts the return to equity stockholders using the presumptive data.

Section -4, uses the real time data and carryout analysis, substantiate and reaffirm the narration of what is shown in section 3.

Model of the problem:

There has always been a challenge for the companies to decide the use of debt in their capital or decide their debt-equity ratio. Some companies use high debt and some don't use debt, companies are under the understanding most of the time that the debt is cheaper than the equity and uses more debt in their capital structure and also they believe that the use of debt is risky, for this reason they refrain from using the debt. This paper seeks to put forth the suitable conditions for applying the debt-equity combination and its positive impact on Return On Equity (ROE).

2.0 : Capital Structure theories revisited:

1) Net Income Approach (NI):

This strategy has been suggested by American economist David Durand. He contends that capital structure choices affect the firm's valuation. It implies that a change in the capital structure results in an equivalent change in the firm's total cost of capital.

According to this strategy, the total cost of capital will decline as the capital structure contains a bigger proportion of debt. This will result in an incline in the firm's worth and, as a result, an increase in the value of the company's equity shares.

The following presumptions form the foundation of the Net Income Approach:

- (i) The expense for debt is lesser than the expense for equity.
- (ii) The investors' perception of risk is unchanged by the debt content.

The Net Income Approach proposes that as financial leverage rises, the average cost of capital will decrease, increasing the firm's value and the market price of equity shares.

2) Net Operating Income Approach :

Mr. David Durand also offered this strategy. Earnings before taxes and interest are known as net operating income. As per this approach, the company's market value is not at all impacted by changes to its capital structure. The firm's capital structure decisions are not important. Additionally, a change in leverage won't affect the firm's overall value or the market share price in any way. The market value of the firm is ascertained by capitalization net operating income at the total cost of capital (K), which is thought to be constant, the market value of the company is determined. By subtracting the market value of the debt from the market value of the company, the market value of the equity is determined.

The following presumptions form the foundation of the net operating income approach:

- (a) No matter how much debt or equity is mixed, the total cost of capital (K) remains unchanged.
- (b) The difference in debt and equity is irrelevant because the market capitalizes the firm's value in total.
- (c) The equity stockholders' risk is increased by the low cost loan. As a result, the equity capitalization rate rises. An rise in the use of debt is offset by a rise in the rate of equity capitalization.

3) Modigliani - Miller Approach (MM)

The Modigliani-Miller strategy offers a behavioral defense for maintaining a constant total cost of capital and total enterprise value. It does not offer an operational defense for why the debt equity mix is irrelevant to the firm's valuation. This method holds that a firm's value is not related to its capital structure. As per

the MM theory, changes to the firm's capital structure or debt-weighted equity mix have no effect on the total cost of capital.

The below mentioned are the three key tenets of the MM approach:

- (1) The capital structure has no bearing on the total cost of capital (K) or the firm's value (V). relatively, "K" and "V" remain unchanged for all ratios of debt to equity. The predicted net operating income (NOI) is capitalized at the rate appropriate for that risk class to determine the firm's overall market value.
- (2) The capitalization rate of a pure equity stream additionally a premium for the financial danger constitutes the cost of equity (Ke). As the capital structure contains more debt, the financial danger rises. As a result, (Ke) rises in a way that precisely balances off the employment of debt as a less expensive source of funding.
- (3) The method of financing an investment has no bearing whatsoever on the cut-off rate for investment purposes.

2.1 Critical review of the aforementioned theories:

- 1) Net Income Approach states; debt is a less expensive source of finance than equity hence, rise in the debt ratio will decrease the total cost of capital, and will lead to increased value of firms.
- 2) Net Operating Income Approach states; total cost of capital will remain the same no matter what is the debt-equity mix, and the value of a firm has no relation with cost of capital or capital structure. When debt levels rise, equity costs rise as well and the overall cost of capital will be offset.
- 3) MM Approach is similar to the Net Operating Income approach, the only difference is that the MM approach provides behavioral justification.

2.2 Conundrum/paradox on cost of equity

All the above capital structure theories discuss either about the cost of capital or about the value of the firm, and the equity capital has been considered as a cost component of capital structure. But it puts under a dilemma when it is looked at the concept of cost of equity,

- *Equity capital is not a fixed cost that the company must pay it regularly.*
- *There is no legal force on the company to pay the cost of equity to its shareholders.*
- *The company can retain its income and reinvest to grow.*

By considering the aforementioned points on equity, it is understandable that the cost of equity is not a reason for concern and capital restructuring to specifically reduce the cost of equity is insignificant. Any company's main objective should be to raise its earnings and distribute them to shareholders, not to cut costs of equity. The cost of equity can be set as a benchmark to reduce the return expectation of its shareholders, not a fixed cost to reduce it.

The study illustrates how the amount of debt increases the earnings of equity stockholders using two alternative assumptive scenarios.

3.0 : Scenario Analysis with Presumptive data

Let's assume that the company has a Capital of Rs: 10,00,000 and the rate of interest on debt is 8% annually.

Scenario one : When the company's Return on capital employed is **14%** and the company Employs only Equity in its capital structure.

EBIT = (10,00,000 x 14%)

All Equity capital Rs.10,00,000	
Earnings before interest and tax (EBIT)	140,000

Less : Interest on debt	Nil
Earnings available to Shareholders (A)	140,000
Equity capital (B)	10,00,000
(A/B) ROE %	14%

Analysis: The above table shows the company as having used only equity capital of Rs 10,00,000. an EBIT of Rs 140,000 and has not used debt, **there is no interest expenses**, earnings available to shareholders is Rs 140,000. The ROE is 14%.

Scenario two : When the company's Return on capital employed is **14%** and the company Employs both **Debt 40%** and **Equity 60%** in their capital structure.

EBIT = (10,00,000 x 14%) Cost of debt is 8%

Debt Rs.400,000 Equity Rs. 600,000	
Earnings before interest and tax	140,000
Less : Interest on debt 400,000 @ 8 % interest	32,000
Earnings available to Shareholders (A)	108,000
Equity capital (B)	600,000
(A/B) ROE %	18%

Analysis: The above table shows the company as having used Debt Rs 400,000 Equity capital of Rs 6,00,000. an EBIT of Rs 140,000 and has used debt, **interest expenses on debt is Rs 32,000** earnings available to shareholders after paying the interest expenses is Rs 108,000. The ROE is **18%**.

Interpretation of above scenarios

Debt not employed

When the firm has not employed debt in its capital structure and earned an ROE of only 14%

Debt Employed

When the company used debt to finance its capital, the ROE grew by 4%, giving a total ROE of 18%.

The company had the same amount of EBIT in the scenarios above, but in scenario one, it had not used debt to fund its capital and had generated ROE of only 14%. However, the company's use of debt in its capital caused the ROE to **improve by 4%**, giving a total ROE of 18%.

From the aforementioned examples, it can be concluded that using some debt in the capital structure of a *profitable company* is preferable because it would boost shareholders' returns which is technically represented as ROE. *Low-profit or loss-making companies would avoid using debt in their capital structure since it would raise their fixed cost commitments and may lead to insolvency.*

4.0 Suggestive Analysis with empirical data

4.1 Data of Gillette India Ltd. for the year 2021 -2022

Currently the company has only Equity as its capital.

Source : <https://www.moneycontrol.com/financials/gilletteindia/balance-sheetVI/GI22>

All Equity Rs. 861.20 Cr	Value in Crores
EBIT	411.33
Interest on Debt	Nil
Earnings available to shareholders (A)	411.33
Equity Capital of Gillette India Ltd.(B)	861.20
(A/B) ROE in %	47.76 %

Analysis: The above table shows Gillette India Ltd as having used only equity capital of Rs 861.20 cr an EBIT of Rs 411.33 Cr and has not used debt, **there is no interest expenses**, earnings available to shareholders is Rs 411.33 cr, Return on equity is 47.76 %

4.2 If the Gillette India Uses 40% debt in its capital structure

Let's assume that the company uses Debt 40% and Equity 60% in their capital structure.

Current total capital of Gillette India Ltd is Rs. 861.20 let's break this into Debt 40% and Equity 60%

Debt 40% = $861.20 \times \frac{40}{100}$ = Rs. 344.48 Cr

Equity 60% = $861.20 \times \frac{60}{100}$ = Rs. 516.72 Cr

Debt Rs. 344.48 Equity Rs. 516.72	Value in Crores
EBIT	411.33
Less: Interest on debt (344.48 @ 8 %)	27.56
Earnings Available to shareholders (A)	383.77
Equity Capital (B)	516.72
(A/B) ROE %	74.27 %

Analysis: The above table shows the company as having used Debt Rs 344.48 Cr. Equity capital of Rs 516.72 Cr. an EBIT of Rs 411.33 Cr. and has used debt, **interest expenses on debt is Rs 27.56 cr**, earnings available to shareholders after paying the interest expenses is Rs 383.77 cr The ROE is 74.27%

Interpretation of suggestive analysis of Gillette India Ltd:

Gillette India Ltd has a relatively higher Return on capital employed (ROCE) but has not employed debt in their capital , without the application of debt the company is earning a **return on equity of 47.76%**.

As per the scenario analysis of this paper when the firm has higher Return on capital employed in such situations firms are preferable to employ debt in their capital, in the suggestive analysis the use of 40% debt in capital structure of Gillette India Ltd has increased the **return on equity to 74.27%**. which increased the ROE by 26.51%

4.3 Data of the Anup Engineering Ltd. or the year 2021 -2022

Currently the company has only Equity in its capital structure.

All Equity Rs. 394.45 Cr	Value in Crores
EBIT	61.92
Interest on Debt	Nil
Earnings available to shareholders (A)	61.92
Equity Capital of Anup Engineering Ltd.(B)	394.45
(A/B) ROE in %	15.69 %

Analysis: The above table shows Anup Engineering Ltd as having used only equity capital of Rs 394.45 cr an EBIT of Rs 61.92 Cr and has not used debt, **there is no interest expenses**, earnings available to shareholders is Rs 61.92 cr, Return on equity is 15.69 %

4.4 If the Anup Engineering Ltd. Uses 40 %debt in its capital structure

Let's assume that the company uses Debt 40% and Equity 60% in their capital structure.

Current total capital of Anup Engineering Ltd is Rs. 394.45 let's break this into Debt 40% and Equity 60%

Debt 40% = $394.45 \times 40/100 = \text{Rs. } 157.78 \text{ Cr}$

Equity 60% = $394.45 \times 60/100 = \text{Rs. } 236.67 \text{ Cr}$

Debt Rs. 157.78 Equity Rs. 236.67	Value in Crores
EBIT	61.92
Less: Interest on debt (157.78 @ 8 %)	12.62
Earnings Available to shareholders (A)	49.3
Equity Capital (B)	236.67
(A/B) ROE %	20.83%

Analysis: The above table shows the company as having used Debt Rs 157.78 Cr Equity capital of Rs 236.67 cr. an EBIT of Rs 61.92 cr and has used debt, **interest expenses on debt is Rs 12.61 cr** earnings available to shareholders after paying the interest expenses is Rs 49.3 cr The return on equity is 20.83%

Interpretation of suggestive analysis of Anup Engineering Ltd:

Anup Engineering Ltd has not employed debt in their capital , without the application of debt the company is earning a **return on equity of 15.69%**

As per the scenario analysis of this paper when the firm has higher Return on capital employed in such situations firms are preferable to employ debt in their capital, in the suggestive analysis the use of 40%

debt in capital structure of Anup Engineering Ltd has increased the **return on equity to 20.83%**. which increased the ROE by 5%

5.0 Conclusion :

Financial function is a core of the business, Profitability is the main focus, companies apply their best knowledge and experience to achieve the best possible outcomes given the constraints. The financial managers have to come out with an ideal debt-equity ratio; the above analysis has been attempted both through the review of existing theories of finance and also through empirical data aimed to elaborate and substantiate as to how companies can use appropriate debt-equity ratio. Through various scenario analysis it was found that there is no such thing as ideal set-all formulae rather under different situations different combinations is worked out. Nonetheless in many such situations when the firm has more return on capital employed it is preferable to employ debt in their capital structure, when companies earn less return on capital employed it is preferable to avoid the use of excessive debt.

References

- 1) GUPTA, S., & SHARMA, R. K. (2018). *Financial Management Theory And Practice (9th ed.)*. Kalyani Publishers.
- 2) Handoo, Anshu & Sharma, Kapil. (2014). *A study on determinants of capital structure in India*. *IIMB Management Review*. 26. 10.1016/j.iimb.2014.07.009.
- 3) Modigliani, F. and M.H. Miller, 1963, *Corporate income taxes and the cost of capital: A correction*, *American Economic Review* 53, 433-43.
- 4) Miller, M.H. and F. Modigliani, 1966, *Some estimates of the cost of capital to the electric utility industry, 1954-57*, *American Economic Review* 56, 333-391.
- 5) Modigliani F. and Miller M.H., *The cost of capital, corporation finance and the theory of investment*, *The American economic review*, 48(3), 261-297 (1958)
- 6) Myers S.C., *The capital structure puzzle*, *The Journal of Finance*, 39(3), 574-592 (1984)
- 7) Friend I. and Lang L.H., *An Empirical Test of the Impact of Managerial Self-interest on Corporate Capital Structure*, *The Journal of Finance*, 43(2), 271-281 (1988)
- 8) Stulz R., *Managerial discretion and optimal financing policies*, *Journal of financial economics*, 26(1), 3-27 (1990)
- 9) Harris M. and Raviv A., *The theory of capital structure*, *The Journal of Finance*, 46(1), 297-355 (1991)
- 10) Baker M. and Wurgler J., *Market timing and capital structure*, *The Journal of Finance*, 57(1), 1-32 (2002)
- 11) W. BAUM~L AND B. MALKIEL, *The firm's optimal debt-equity combination and the cost of capital*, *Quart. J. Econ.* 81 (1967), 547-578. 3. J. I. BULOW AND J. B. SHOVEN. *The bankruptcy d*
- 12) Shyam Sunder L. and C Myers S., *Testing static tradeoff against pecking order models of capital structure*, *Journal of financial economics*, 51(2), 219-244 (1999)
- 13) Abor, J. (2005), "The effect of Capital structure on profitability: an empirical analysis of listed firms in Ghana", *The Journal of Risk Finance*, Vol. 6 No. 5, pp. 438-445
- 14) Paul Rajan, Arun Prakash. (2016). *A Study on Impact of Leverage ON Profitability: Empirical Evidence from Select Pharmaceutical Companies in India*. 6. 1036-1043.
- 15) Tariq Zafar, Sayed. (2011). "A Study on Impact of Leverage on the Profitability of Indian Banking Industry" Published by Publishing Indian Group in *International Journal of Financial Management*, ISSN, NO.2229-5682 (P), an International Referred Quarterly Journal, pp.85-99. Published by

Publishing Indian Group in International Journal of Financial Management, ISSN, NO.2229-5682 (P), an International Referred Quarterly Journal, pp.85-99. Vol.4. 85-99.

- 16) Abor, J. (2005). *The effect of capital structure on profitability: An empirical analysis of listed firms in Ghana. Journal of Risk Finance, 6(5), 438-447.*
- 17) Hirshleifer D. and Thakor A.V., *Managerial conservatism, project choice, and debt, Review of financial studies, 5(3), 437-470 (1992)*
- 18) Kim W.S. and Sorensen E.H., *Evidence on the impact of the agency costs of debt on corporate debt policy, Journal of Financial and Quantitative analysis, 21(2), 131-144 (1986)*
- 19) Harris, Milton and Artur Raviv, 1990. *Capital structure and the informational role of debt. Journal of Finance 45. 321-350.*
- 20) Hart, Oliver and John Moore, 1989. *Default and renegotiation: A dynamic model of debt, Unpublished working paper (MIT. Cambridge. MA).*